

SCOSS STRATEGY

2025
2027

SCOSS

SUSTAINING THE OPEN

MISSION

We create connections to sustain vital Open Science infrastructure.

VISION

A world where research is supported by a sustainable and thriving ecosystem of Open Science infrastructure.

VALUES

- Community-led
- Expert-driven
- Global in reach
- Collaborative
- Equitable and inclusive
- Practical and outcome-driven

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services (SCOSS) plays a crucial role in securing the future of non-commercial Open Science infrastructure by helping them to secure their sustainability.

Since its founding in 2017, over €6.4m has been committed to infrastructure providers and the SCOSS family has grown to nearly 20 organizations.

This strategy seeks to build on that success; it sets out SCOSS's goals for the next three years and the steps SCOSS will take to achieve them.

SCOSS's goals for the period 2025 to 2027 will be:

- **GOAL 1** - Foster the strength and sustainability of the Open Science infrastructure ecosystem
- **GOAL 2** - Diversify support for Open Science infrastructure through new relationships and connection-building
- **GOAL 3** - Mainstream the funding of Open Science infrastructure

CONTEXT

The Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services (SCOSS) is a network of organizations raising funds and awareness to secure the future of non-commercial infrastructure providers supporting Open Access and Open Science.

SCOSS was founded in 2017 when commercial providers were acquiring many Open Science infrastructure providers or considering ceasing operations due to unsustainable business models or the end of project-based funding. It was established to encourage stakeholders in the research sector to consider the consequences if open infrastructure was lost and to encourage them to actively prevent this through support and funding.

SCOSS does not offer a single, once-and-for-all solution, but it is a pragmatic initiative to address some of the sustainability challenges facing Open Science infrastructure providers. The initiative prioritizes an action-oriented approach, supporting selected infrastructure and service providers (now considered 'the SCOSS Family') by promoting them toward a community of supporters – institutions, funders, and consortia. We seek to identify innovative approaches to supporting Open Science infrastructure providers and to complement funding mechanisms that may emerge from other organizations.

Via a rigorous application and assessment process, SCOSS offers a small number of selected infrastructure providers access to its community of funding supporters worldwide. SCOSS has been through five funding rounds, with a sixth launched late in 2024. Well over €6.4m has been pledged by the community since the beginning of 2017. At the beginning of 2025, the SCOSS Family has grown to include almost 20 organizations, providing a global, stable set of Open Science infrastructure providers.

The geopolitical climate has changed since 2017, making international collaborative initiatives more complex but more important than ever. Stakeholders across the research ecosystem have less funding and less discretionary funding available to them; SCOSS supporters are no exception to this development, but they remain committed to supporting Open Science. As a result, SCOSS's role has become all the more critical.

GOALS AND PRIORITIES

GOAL 1

Foster the strength and sustainability of the Open Science infrastructure ecosystem

SCOSS was created to address an urgent and immediate need to support Open Science infrastructure. Ensuring the long-term sustainability of organizations is a deeper challenge, however. SCOSS focuses on promoting two types of sustainability in the infrastructures it supports.

- Financial - the ability to generate resources to meet the needs of the present without compromising the future.
- Programmatic - the ability to develop, mature, and cycle out programs to be responsive to constituencies over time.

SCOSS seeks to help infrastructure organizations develop without creating a dependency. SCOSS's application process is designed to encourage organizations to consider and articulate how they can develop a sustainable model and set milestones to help them achieve this.

The process has evolved in response to feedback from applicants and the SCOSS Advisory Group and will continue to do so. The SCOSS Family Community of Practice is now larger and more well-established and serves to support infrastructures in building operational capacity.

In 2025-27, SCOSS will continue to reduce complexity wherever possible, both for those applying for SCOSS endorsement and for those seeking to fund the endorsed infrastructures.

GOALS AND PRIORITIES

GOAL 1

Foster the strength and sustainability of the Open Science infrastructure ecosystem

Priorities

- Select and support Open Science infrastructure providers that have the potential to achieve financial and programmatic sustainability.
- Seek to maintain funding levels for SCOSS-endorsed Open Science infrastructure providers.
- Continue to support the SCOSS Family as an ecosystem of interoperable Open Science infrastructure providers.

GOALS AND PRIORITIES

GOAL 2

Diversify support for Open Science infrastructure through new relationships and connection-building

SCOSS creates connections between its global community and selected infrastructure providers. In an environment of growing pressure on institutional budgets and research funding, SCOSS will seek to add new supporters and continue building connections among the SCOSS Family to strengthen its resilience.

Libraries will continue to play a central role in the SCOSS community, but many other entities in the research community benefit from open infrastructure. SCOSS will continue to build connections outside the library, seeking input and engagement from other departments within research institutions and from research funders and building relationships with consortia and networks that bring together libraries and other stakeholder groups. SCOSS will continue to operate globally, seeking supporters from all continents and supporting infrastructure providers who operate globally.

Priorities

- Maintain the current supporter base and seek the addition of new supporters.
- Continue the work of the SCOSS Family Community of Practice by facilitating communication and collaboration across the network and learning from common experiences.
- Facilitate greater sharing of experiences between different supporters to spread innovative and best funding practices and to develop greater institutional memory across them.

GOALS AND PRIORITIES

GOAL 3

Mainstream the funding of Open Science infrastructure

SCOSS acts as an intermediary, signalling the trustworthiness of a select number of infrastructure providers by undertaking assessments and making recommendations. SCOSS will continue to advocate for the value of supporting independent, interoperable infrastructure providers. The growth of the SCOSS Family over time into a set of stable, global infrastructure providers also adds to its credibility.

SCOSS will continue to advocate for supporting Open Science infrastructure. It emphasizes that open infrastructures help institutions achieve flexibility and independence from commercial providers that require users to lock into their 'walled gardens' of proprietary infrastructure. Supporting Open Science infrastructure may be a charitable act for some, but for most, it is an investment in institutional capacity and capabilities and offers greater value for money.

Priorities

- Support applicants who demonstrate:
 - value to the community
 - commitment to appropriate governance structures
 - transparency in finances and operations
 - interoperability with other Open Science infrastructure
 - adoption of open practices in their operations.
- Build the case that Open Science infrastructure providers are trustworthy and offer greater control and value than commercial alternatives.
- Engage in capacity building to increase the understanding of open infrastructure's value proposition and how to implement operational frameworks that support it.

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